

Red Temple/Temple D2 (Tell Mardikh/ancient Ebla)

also known as “Kura’s Temple on the Acropolis”

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Entry tags: Temple, northern Levant, Religious Group, north-western inner Syria, Early Bronze IVA (mature Early Syrian Period), Near East, Early Bronze Age, Ancient Syrian Religion, Religious Place, Archaeological monument, Temple Buildings and Temple Cult

The Red Temple (Temple D2) is a monumental temple building erected in the ancient city of Ebla (present-day Tell Mardikh). It dates back to the age of the Royal Archives of the great Early Syrian town, c. 2400–2300 BCE (in the traditional conventional chronology), that is the Early Bronze IVA of north-western inland Syria chronology: it must have been built in an advanced phase of Early Bronze IVA, around 2350 BCE, as it was erected after a north peripheral sector of the West Unit of the Royal Palace had been dismissed and razed. It is so far the only identified cult building belonging to the age of the Archives, along with the Temple of the Rock in the Lower Town South-East: together with the Archive’ texts, these two sanctuaries offer crucial insights into the religious phenomena in Ebla and Syria in the mature Early Syrian Period; and provide evidence of the unity and specificity of the religious architectural tradition of inland Syria in the central part of the third millennium BCE, when the in-antis temple model spreads. The Red Temple has been excavated in Area D, underneath the imposing Old Syrian Ishtar’s Temple dating to the Middle Bronze I-II. The temple was built on the western edge of the Acropolis and near the Royal Palace G, overlooking from the north the imposing ceremonial and administrative wings of the palace itself. It has certainly to be identified with the Temple of Kura within the SA.ZA (the central palatine administrative complex of the mature Early Syrian town) and represented the dynastic sanctuary of the lords of Ebla. Kura was, in fact, the patron god of the city and the main divinity of Ebla in the second half of the third millennium BCE. For this reason, the dynastic temple of the Old Syrian Period, dedicated to the great goddess Ishtar, new patron deity of the Eblaite dynasty, was built over its ruins. As described in the text of the “Ritual of Kingship”, the elaborate ritual of the renewal of kingship, which began at the Temple of Kura near the town wall and the Kura Gate (now identified with the Temple of the Rock), and which involved a series of ritual acts and pilgrimages performed together by the king and queen, concluded in this temple with the enthronement of the royal couple. At the same time as the king and the queen entered the temple, the cult statues of Kura and Barama (the supreme divine couple) entered the building. The temple (some 24.20 m long and 17 m wide) takes its name from the dark red colour of its bricks. It was oriented with the entrance towards south, like the later Middle Bronze I-II Ishtar’s Temple on the same place. It adheres to the typology of the in antis temple, well attested in the Syro-Levantine religious architecture from the mid-third millennium BCE. It has a moderately longroom – almost square – cella (L.9980), nearly 10.20 m long by 9.40 m wide, and a rather deep vestibule (L.9990), 6.70 m long by 9.40 m wide, delimited by projecting antae. The building features strong similarities with the Temple of the Rock for its typology, size, and proportions. However, in the Red Temple four columns divided the cella into three small naves and two further columns formed a porch in the vestibule; the column bases were massive limestone cylinders. Finally, three steps of accurately worked limestone slabs formed a short entrance staircase to the vestibule porch. The temple had thick walls (about 3.60/3.80 m); while at all four corners of the building there were low buttresses, approximately 0.20/0.30 m. The Red Temple was destroyed at the same time as the whole settlement of the age of the Royal Archives, at the end of Early Bronze IVA, around 2300 BCE (Matthiae 2021, pp. 65–83, 301–303).

Date Range: 2400 BCE - 2300 BCE

Region: Ebla/ Tell Mardikh

Region tags: Syria, North-western inner Syria

The archaeological site of Tell Mardikh, ancient Ebla, is located in upper inner Syria, 55 km south of Aleppo. The site has an extension of 56 hectares. It has been continuously excavated by an archaeological expedition of the Sapienza University of Rome between 1964 and 2010, for 47 uninterrupted campaigns, which brought to light the large fortified urban settlements of the Early Bronze and Middle Bronze Ages (mature/late Early Syrian Period and Old Syrian Period).

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Acropolis of the Early Syrian town

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

A single structure

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

Notes: some 24.20 m long and 17 m wide

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A group of structures:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A group of features:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

– Political

Notes: The Red Temple has to be identified with the Temple of Kura within the SAZA (the central palatine administrative complex). It represented the dynastic sanctuary of the lords of the great Early Syrian town of Ebla. Kura was the patron god of the city and the main divinity of Ebla in the second half of the third millennium BCE. As described in the text of the "Ritual of Kingship", the

elaborate ritual of the renewal of kingship, which began at the Temple of Kura near the town wall and the Kura Gate (now identified with the Temple of the Rock), concluded in this temple with the enthronement of the royal couple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– Yes

Notes: The Red Temple was destroyed at the same time as the whole settlement of the age of the Royal Archives, at the end of Early Bronze IVA, around 2300 BCE (in the traditional conventional chronology).

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità* 15 (2009): 43-83.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

Notes: The conquest and devastation possibly carried out by Sargon of Akkad.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

– Human-caused accident

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: However, the location of the remains of the temple maintained its sacrality. During the Early Bronze IVB (late Early Syrian Period) a more modest temple (Temple D3) was built over the northern sector of the ruins of the Red Temple, until the much larger and monumental Ishtar's Temple was erected during the first decades of the second millennium BCE and became the new dynastic temple of the Old Syrian city.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon, probably the lord of fresh waters who resided in the abyss. The Eblaite god Kura was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions (he may be considered as an archaic analogue of El, distinguished by chthonic rather than celestial features); he was the patron god of the city and patron of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. He resided in the main temple at SA.ZA, where he received offerings more copious than all the other gods.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

- Source 1: Matthiae, P. 2021. *Ebla : Archaeology and History* . London / New York : Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.
- Source 2: Matthiae, P. 2009. Temples and Queens at Ebla. Recent Discoveries in a Syrian Metropolis between Mesopotamia, Egypt and the Levant, in *Interconnections in the Eastern Mediterranean. Lebanon in the Bronze and Iron Ages. Proceedings of the International Symposium Beirut 2008 (BAAL, Hors-Série VI)*. Beirut: Ministère de la Culture, Direction Générale des Antiquités, pp. 117-139.
- Source 3: Matthiae, P. 2009. Temples et reines de l'Ébla protosyrienne : résultats des fouilles à Tell Mardikh en 2007 et 2008, in *Comptes rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres*, 153e année, n. 2, 2009. pp. 747-791.

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Type of feature

- Other [specify]: The temple was built by razing the northern end of the West Unit of the Central Complex of the Royal Palace G.

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

- Scientific

↳ Years of excavation:

–Year range: 2008

↳ Name of excavation

–Official or descriptive name: Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Ebla (MAIS)

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– No

Notes: However, the temple was isolated and independent from the adjacent buildings.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Notes: The temple was built on the western edge of the Acropolis and near the Royal Palace G, overlooking from the north the imposing ceremonial and administrative wings of the palace itself.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla; possibly Ishar-Damu, the last king of the city before its destruction by Sargon of Akkad.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Temples Et Reines De L'ébla Protosyrienne : Résultats Des Fouilles À Tell Mardikh En 2007 Et 2008". *Comptes Rendus Des Séances De L'académie Des Inscriptions Et Belles-lettres*, 153e année, no. 2 (2009): 747–91. <https://doi.org/10.3406/crai.2009.92536>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Notes: The temple was built north of the Royal Palace G, overlooking the ceremonial and administrative wings of the palace itself.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: But we can report that an administrative text belonging to the reign of king Ishar-Damu (TM:75.G.1464, r. XIV 12-17) mentions the delivery of 50 silver mines "to make the temple of Kura" on the Acropolis (Pomponio - Xella 1997, p. 238, n. 184).

Reference: Pomponio, Francesco , and Paolo Xella. *Les Dieux D'ebbla - Étude Analytique Des Divinités Éblaïtes À L'époque Des Archives Royales Du liie Millénaire* (AOAT 245). Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 1997.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion with expectation of protection over the ruling dynasty

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Matthiae, P. 2021. *Ebla : Archaeology and History* . London / New York : Routledge Taylor & Francis Group.

– Source 2: Matthiae, P. 2009. *Temples and Queens at Ebla. Recent Discoveries in a Syrian Metropolis between Mesopotamia, Egypt and the Levant*, in *Interconnections in the Eastern Mediterranean. Lebanon in the Bronze and Iron Ages. Proceedings of the International Symposium Beirut 2008 (BAAL, Hors-Série VI)*. Beirut: Ministère de la Culture, Direction Générale des Antiquités, pp. 117-139.

– Source 3: Matthiae, P. 2009. *Temples et reines de l'Ébla protosyrienne : résultats des fouilles à Tell Mardikh en 2007 et 2008*, in *Comptes rendus des séances de l'Académie des Inscriptions et Belles-Lettres*, 153e année, n. 2, 2009. pp. 747-791.

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– Yes

Type of excavation:

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Years of excavation:

– Year range: 2008

Name of excavation

– Official or descriptive name: Missione Archeologica Italiana in Siria, Ebla (MAIS)

Topographical Context

Is the place associated with a feature in the landscape

– Elevation

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Type of elevation

– Other [specify]: Acropolis of the Early Syrian town

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Type of feature

– Other [specify]: The temple was built by razing the northern end of the West Unit of the Central Complex of the Royal Palace G.

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

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Notes: However, the temple was isolated and independent from the adjacent buildings.

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Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer once for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

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Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

A single structure

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Specific to this answer:

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↳ The structure has a definite shape

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Notes: some 24.20 m long and 17 m wide

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A group of structures:

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Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ A group of features:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Worship:

– Communal

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

– Political

Notes: The Red Temple has to be identified with the Temple of Kura within the SAZA (the central palatine administrative complex). It represented the dynastic sanctuary of the lords of the great Early Syrian town of Ebla. Kura was the patron god of the city and the main divinity of Ebla in the second half of the third millennium BCE. As described in the text of the "Ritual of

Kingship”, the elaborate ritual of the renewal of kingship, which began at the Temple of Kura near the town wall and the Kura Gate (now identified with the Temple of the Rock), concluded in this temple with the enthronement of the royal couple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

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↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

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Notes: The Red Temple was destroyed at the same time as the whole settlement of the age of the Royal Archives, at the end of Early Bronze IVA, around 2300 BCE (in the traditional conventional chronology).

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Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ How was the structure/feature destroyed

– Burned

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was it destroyed deliberately:

–As the result of war

Notes: The conquest and devastation possibly carried out by Sargon of Akkad.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Was it destroyed by accident/natural phenomena:

–Human-caused accident

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– No

Notes: However, the location of the remains of the temple maintained its sacrality. During the Early Bronze IVB (late Early Syrian Period) a more modest temple (Temple D3) was built over the northern sector of the ruins of the Red Temple, until the much larger and monumental Ishtar's Temple was erected during the first decades of the second millennium BCE and became the new dynastic temple of the Old Syrian city.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

– Yes [specify]: God Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon, probably the lord of fresh waters who resided in the abyss. The Eblaite god Kura was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions (he may be considered as an archaic analogue of El, distinguished by chthonic rather than celestial features); he was the patron god of the city and patron of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. He resided in the main temple at SA.ZA, where he received offerings more copious than all the other gods.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Specify

– King or emperor

– Other [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla; possibly Ishar-Damu, the last king of the city before its destruction by Sargon of Akkad.

Reference: Matthiae, Paolo. "Temples Et Reines De L'ébla Protosyrienne : Résultats Des Fouilles À Tell Mardikh En 2007 Et 2008". *Comptes Rendus Des Séances De L'académie Des Inscriptions Et Belles-lettres*, 153e année, no. 2 (2009): 747-91. <https://doi.org/10.3406/crai.2009.92536>.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the creation of the place sponsored by an external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Notes: But we can report that an administrative text belonging to the reign of king Ishar-Damu (TM:75.G.1464, r. XIV 12-17) mentions the delivery of 50 silver mines "to make the temple of Kura" on the Acropolis (Pomponio - Xella 1997, p. 238, n. 184).

Reference: Pomponio, Francesco , and Paolo Xella. Les Dieux D'ebla - Étude Analytique Des Divinités Éblaïtes À L'époque Des Archives Royales Du Iiie Millénaire (AOAT 245). Münster: Ugarit-Verlag, 1997.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Expression of devotion with expectation of protection over the ruling dynasty

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Design and Material Remains

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 410

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Plaster

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Foundations (comprising two rows of medium- sized stones) and column bases

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– No

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s).

Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:

Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.

– Square meters: 410

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

↳ Clay
– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Plaster
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Wood

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Grass

– Yes

Notes: Used to make mudbricks

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Stone

– Yes

Notes: Foundations (comprising two rows of medium- sized stones) and column bases

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Decoration

Is decoration present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Beliefs and Practices

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the Ritual of Kingship. The Red Temple has certainly to be identified with the Temple of Kura within the SAZA (the central palatine administrative complex of the mature Early Syrian town) and represented the dynastic sanctuary of the lords of the great Early Syrian town of Ebla. As described in the text of the "Ritual of Kingship", the elaborate ritual of kingship, which began at the Temple of Kura near the town wall and the Kura Gate (now identified with the Temple of the Rock) and involved a series of ritual acts and pilgrimages performed together by the king and queen, concluded in this temple with the enthronement of the royal couple. At the same time as the king and the queen entered the temple, the cult statues of Kura and Barama (the supreme divine couple) entered the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The god Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon in the age of the Archives. He was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss. He was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions, patron god of the city and protector of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. He remains the most obscure deity appearing in the written documents from the third quarter of the third millennium BCE. However, he does not seem to differ much from the type of Dagan of Tuttul, and he also had paternal and celestial attributions similar to those which, in the second millennium BCE, must have belonged to El (in the pantheon of Ugarit). Kura's (and Ishkhara's) prominence in the city of the Archives points to archaic character of the religious system of Early Syrian Ebla and reveals a situation preceding the full establishment of gods like Adda/Hadad and Ashtar/Ishtar in Syria and Upper Mesopotamia. According to written sources, two temples closely associated with the kingship were erected to Kura: a temple, close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura, where, at the beginning of the celebrations for the renewal of kingship, the queen entered the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the city walls; a second temple within the SAZA, the central palatine administrative complex, where the elaborate ritual of kingship concluded with the enthronement of the royal couple at the end of a pilgrimage to the shrines of their deified ancestors.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura possibly had celestial attributions.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through monarch:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ By all the community

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla, the elite members and the priesthood.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are grave goods present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are formal burials present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

Notes: The god Kura, chief god of the Eblaite pantheon in the age of the Archives. He was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss. He was a god with paternal and possibly celestial attributions, patron god of the city and protector of the lords of the great Early Syrian town. He remains the most obscure deity appearing in the written documents from the third quarter of the third millennium BCE. However, he does not seem to differ much from the type of Dagan of Tuttul, and he also had paternal and celestial attributions similar to those which, in the second millennium BCE, must have belonged to El (in the pantheon of Ugarit). Kura's (and Ishkhara's) prominence in the city of the Archives points to archaic character of the religious system of Early Syrian Ebla and reveals a situation preceding the full establishment of gods like Adda/Hadad and Ashtar/Ishtar in Syria and Upper Mesopotamia. According to written sources, two temples closely associated with the kingship were erected to Kura: a temple, close to the town wall and the Gate of Kura, where, at the beginning of the celebrations for the renewal of kingship, the queen entered the city after waiting for sunrise in the fields outside the city walls; a second temple within the SAZA, the central palatine administrative complex, where the elaborate ritual of kingship concluded with the enthronement of the royal couple at the end of a pilgrimage to the shrines of their deified ancestors.

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura possibly had celestial attributions.

↳ Are they chthonic (underworld)

– Yes

Notes: The Eblaite god Kura was probably the lord of fresh waters, who resided in the abyss.

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are they other:

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Does the supreme high god communicate with the living at this place:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In waking, everyday life:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In dreams:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ In trance possession:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Through divination practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Only through monarch:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are previously human spirits present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are nonhuman supernatural beings present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are mixed human-divine beings present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

Notes: E.g., the Ritual of Kingship. The Red Temple has certainly to be identified with the Temple of Kura within the SAZA (the central palatine administrative complex of the mature Early Syrian town) and represented the dynastic sanctuary of the lords of the great Early Syrian town of Ebla. As described in the text of the "Ritual of Kingship", the elaborate ritual of kingship, which began at the Temple of Kura near the town wall and the Kura Gate (now identified with the Temple of the Rock) and involved a series of ritual acts and pilgrimages performed together by the king and queen, concluded in this temple with the enthronement of the royal couple. At the same time as the king and the queen entered the temple, the cult statues of Kura and Barama (the supreme divine couple) entered the temple.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are material offerings present:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings composed of valuable objects:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings composed of daily-life objects:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are material offerings interred at this place (in caches):

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ By all the community

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ By specific individuals

–Yes [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla, the elite members and the priesthood.

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is it required:

– Yes

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is there cleansing (for the maintenance):

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Are there periodic repairs/reconstructions:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Is the maintenance performed by permanent staff:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

↳ Other

– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– No

Specific to this answer:

Status of Participants: ✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Present part time

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Yes

Present full time

– Field doesn't know

Present part time

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific sex/gender:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific ethnicity:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists of specific class/cast:

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists dedicated to the place for life:

– Field doesn't know

Are the religious specialists stratified in a hierarchical system:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– No

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:

Institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders

– Yes

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– No

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– No

Are there scriptures associated with this place:

– No

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Reference: Yes, Matthiae, Paolo. "Crisis and Collapse: Similarity and Diversity in the Three Destructions of Ebla from EB IVA to MB II". *Scienze Dell'antichità 15* (2009): 43-83.

Reference: King or emperor, Other [specify]: The lords of the great Early Syrian city of Ebla; possibly Ishar-Damu, the last king of the city before its destruction by Sargon of Akkad., Matthiae, Paolo. "Temples Et Reines De L'ébla Protosyrienne : Résultats Des Fouilles À Tell Mardikh En 2007 Et 2008". *Comptes Rendus Des Séances De L'académie Des Inscriptions Et Belles-lettres*, 153e année, no. 2 (2009): 747-91. <https://doi.org/10.3406/crai.2009.92536>.